

Social Science: Introduction to Social Science

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Abstract:- Sociology is an ancient science. There is no science other than social science. Humans are social creatures. We live in society all our lives. Society teaches us a lot and we learn it from society. The basic foundation of this society is social science. Just as society cannot function without social science, so we cannot function without society. So the importance of social science in human life is many times more than other sciences.

Keywords:- *Aacquiring knowledge, Sociology, Aancient science, Emergence, Bbehavior.*

I. INTRODUCTION

In acquiring knowledge, man has not only tried to know himself, he has equally tried to acquire knowledge about his environment. The interrelationship of the natural environment with it is a matter of Human interdependence and it is part of the physical sciences. Sociology has developed by being deeply related to these subjects. It is necessary to have a general knowledge about a subject before first focusing on its subject in practice. In order to achieve this objective, we are briefly discussing the concepts related to sociology according to the views of different sociologists.

II. WHAT DOES SOCIAL SCIENCE DISCUSS?

What is the content of this discussion and its limitations? These questions are still Being discussed. In fact, it is not possible for anyone to say which major issue was properly discussed first. It never appears As a complete essay from a human thought. In fact, discussions from different angles come together on a subject and that subject is given a special name. The subject of sociology has also developed in this way. The term sociology was first coined by the French Philosopher Augustus Conte (Auguste Comte, 1798-1857) in the fourth volume of his Course-de-Philosophy Positive, published in 1839, for which he is called the father of sociology. He first named it 'Social Physics' to give a scientific status to the necessity of creating a science in the society. But when it became known that a Bezian mathematician had used the experiment as an introduction to social issues about four years ago, August Conte changed his mind and named the new science 'Sociology'. His main consideration was how sociology as a science could be based on systematic observations and class divisions without resorting to any authoritarian instruction or conjecture.

III. DEFINITION OF SOCIAL SCIENCE

Sociology, like other social sciences, has a special definition. Different sociologists have defined sociology differently. It is a difficult task to explain in one word the sociology that reviews the whole social life. So we see so many differences among sociologists over the definition of sociology.

As social thought flows in different fields, sociological groups of different ideologies have emerged. On the one hand the abundance of elements of modern sociology and on the other hand its multifaceted analysis and perspectives have created multiple definitions of sociology. Social thinking develops from the very beginning of social life. In the evolving trend of social life, the flow of change also comes in the world of thought. That is why sociologists of this age have conducted studies and researches on the basis of social phenomena in terms of realities in special cases. Robert Beers tad's comment on sociology is, "Sociology, on the one hand, is based on primitive human thought. Old, on the other hand, new according to the daily newspaper. " (The story of sociology is as old as human thought and as new as the day's newspaper.)'

We see that all sociologists have tried to give an acceptable definition of sociology in terms of their own point of view. In giving this definition, one sociologist has shown predominance in one subject or sociology has given the name to study Gaeta society. As a result, in some cases the definition is becoming one-sided, again it has become short. As a result, it becomes difficult to analyze the subject or event and it is difficult to fully understand the subject; For example, Sumner and Frank ward define sociology as the science of society and the science of social phenomena. Sociologists Durkheim and Kovalevsky called sociology "science of institution" and "science of social organization and social change", respectively. Sociologist Simel said that the science of human relationship. Sociologist Max Weber called it "the science of social action." Small said, 'Science of Social Process' and Parke said, 'Science of Collective Behavior'.

IV. THE ORIGIN OF SOCIAL SCIENCE

Sociology did not develop as a separate science until the middle of the nineteenth century. The identity of sociology as a separate branch of knowledge like other social sciences is not long.

Just as man wanted to know and understand nature as easily as man wanted to know his society by instinct. There

is no end to his search. As a result of this research, we first find philosophy. In ancient times Socrates, Plato, Aristotle and Pythagoras considered sciences to be part philosophy. They review the social sciences as part of the philosophy. And philosophy seems to have been able to hold all kinds of research in its embrace with great success.

In ancient Greece and Rome, human thought developed through various countermeasures. In seeking the relationship between the world and life, the ancient thinkers sought the sociological or sociological direction.

Discussions about society and the state abound in the writings of ancient Greek and Roman scholars. However, in their writings, such as the discussion of social relations. The society and the state were not discussed separately as they were influenced by political issues. Yet the main purpose of their efforts was to discuss an ideal social life. Such as the philosopher Plato (420-348 BC). Republic's The Republic reviews various social issues and questions. Aristotle's (364-322 BC) The Politics and The Ethics are the first to cover law, society and the state.

V. BRANCHES OF SOCIAL SCIENCE

Following are some different branches of Social Science;

A. Applied Social Science

W. E. According to Marr, the application of sociological principles to the analysis of social relations in a particular context is called applied sociology. According to Gilder, the main goal of applied sociology is to predict specific social and cultural changes and to bring about change. Although it falls within the scope of crisis or relationship analysis arising from specific social backgrounds, its main theme is the change of social structure.

Sociology of Law: The sociology of law is to examine the law created by the people in the society and its validity. The main purpose. Discusses how the law works through other institutions of society and in some cases the application of the law is inevitable.

The study of the sociology of law in Europe has been well received. But it is not so well supported in America and Britain. In fact, in modern times many sociologists are reluctant to look at the sociology of law. But among the sociologists at an early stage of the development of sociology, Durkheim and Max Weber focused on the sociology of law. Durkheim analyzed the laws of vengeance with primitive societies and compensatory laws with modern industrial societies. Max Weber also analyzes the sociological significance of rationalist law, especially in the context of Western Society. After them, the Australian scholar E. E. Ehrlich published an important research work on the sociology of law, which was published in 1938 in the form of a book entitled Fundamental Principles of the Sociology of Law. The interest in this scripture can be seen in the context of the encouragement of some American jurists in modern times.

B. Economic Social Science

Many modern sociologists analyze various aspects of human economic life. Has made a valuable contribution. Examples include economic issues such as industrial organizations, industrial development, production problems, wages, labor divisions, labor unions, property, inheritance, and so on. The sociological analysis of these economic issues is becoming more and more popular. As a result modern. A new branch of sociology called 'Economic Sociology' has been created. The discussion of the social role of economic institutions is called 'economic sociology'.

C. Political Social Science

The main point of political sociology is to have political structures and institutions and social structures and institutions side by side. The basic premise of this scripture is to analyze the new types of problems that are being created as a result of their interaction. The field of political sociology has been created as the discussion of different parts of the state apparatus has been influenced by the content of sociologists today.

D. Social Science of Education

Sociology of Education. With the expansion of the field, the branch of education called 'Sociology of Education' has emerged in the context of acquiring knowledge of the people in the society and building on its institutional infrastructure. August Conte is called the father of sociology. But more than that, E. George Payne is said to be the father of the sociology of education. This word is valuable. Emphasizing the need for continuous interaction between the individual and the environment, he said that the sociology of education means a science-based subject in which descriptions and explanations of social group institutions and methods are found.

Basically, it is through these social relationships or through these that the individual acquires and organizes his experiences. The behavior of an individual from birth to death is conditional on his or her cultural environment. The sociology of education, however, has included some of its subjects. He did not stop at discussing specific educational institutions, i.e. schools. He has embraced family, playmates, religious institutions, the exchange of ideas, and even a wider field of Lake Culture, among many other things.

“The current state of the sociology of education, Herrington summarizes the opinions of teachers obtained during research on the subject. Education is a specific goal of sociology:

- To realize the role of teachers in schools as a facilitator of social development and as a place for reflection of different ideologies of the society.
- Understanding the cultural, economic and social trends of democracy in the context of traditional and other educational institutions.
- Understand the effects of social forces and their effects on the individual.
- Socialization of the curriculum.
- Adequate analytical thinking and research methods to achieve the right purpose.

E. Industrial Social Science

The emergence of sociology in the context of the revolutionary changes that took place in social life after the Industrial Revolution in England in the eighteenth century. That is why sociology is called emerging art. The science of society'. In fact, the purpose of industrial society theory is to discuss the interaction of industrial production system and social structure.

F. Social Science of Art and Literature

Different parts of what we mean by social culture are intertwined in such a way that the whole culture achieves a temporary stable equilibrium. This complex overall culture is the heritage of the people of a society. Literary researchers try to understand the different relational character of this social tradition. The different types of relationships that develop between a particular society and its consciousness are reflected in art literature. People live in society. A person is socially involved through various kinds of relationships with other people in the society. Literature, art, ideals, theories, social customs, laws and methods of communicating with others through language are all based on social relations, no matter how major or minor. Basically there is no such thing as a social relationship. Changes in style in industry are related to the type of change in social structure. Such roles of industry in different production systems can take different shapes. Thus, from the effort to study art and literature in the context of social system, a branch called sociology of art and literature has developed as a distinct branch of sociology.

VI. THE IMPORTANCE OF THE STUDY OF SOCIAL SCIENCE

There are some critics among sociologists who think that sociology does not discuss the realities of life, but only theories and theories. Reviewing the important concepts of sociology, it is easy to understand that the need for discussion of this scripture is very high among the people of the society.

Sociologist Kingsley Davis, in his book *Human Society* on the necessity of sociology lessons, states: "It is clear that sociology lessons have social and personal value. That is why the presence of the society has not acknowledged but supported it. "Not only does such study value (by almost any standard one adopts) but in a complex so it becomes indispensable."From this we can easily understand the need for sociology lessons:

VII. CONCLUSION

Sociology is an ancient science. There is no science other than social science. Humans are social creatures. We live in society all our lives. Society teaches us a lot and we learn it from society. The basic foundation of this society is social science. Just as society cannot function without social science, so we cannot function without society. So the importance of social science in human life is many times more than other sciences.

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